

THE POSSIBILITY OF PRINTING ON BIOPOLYMER PACKAGING MATERIALS

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Abstract: *In the realm of packaging, there has been a long-standing tradition of utilizing a significant amount of plastic materials. However, there is an increasing demand within the food packaging sector to shift away from petrochemical-based packaging materials and adopt more environmentally friendly biodegradable alternatives. Biodegradable packaging materials derived from natural sources have the potential to address the issue of disposing synthetic plastics. Using biodegradable polymers for packaging production, partial solution to the problem of accumulating solid waste comprised of conventional non-biodegradable polymers can be offered. Particularly, there is a notable interest in utilizing biopolymers derived from agricultural and industrial waste. The objective of this scientific research is to explore the feasibility of printing on biopolymer materials used in packaging, considering the need to display essential information on the packaged products. Specifically, chitosan and gelatin were selected as the materials for the samples. To conduct the research, a test chart containing a QR code was generated, and the UVLED printing technology (Apex 1610 machine), was employed. Following the printing process, the samples were subjected to both visual and objective analyses. The objective analysis involved assessing the legibility of the QR code, thereby determining the accuracy of the printed content, including the intricate thin lines within the code. The findings of the study indicate the need for further investigation in this field.*

Keywords: biopolymers, chitosan, gelatin, printing

1 INTRODUCTION

Biopolymers, also known as IV generation packaging, are self-destructive, biodegradable materials, obtained from renewable resources. As macromolecular substances, natural polymers or biopolymers can be found in nature as parts of plant or animal tissues (Lazić and Novaković, 2010).

It can be argued that biopolymers are among the most environmentally friendly packaging materials due to their complete ecological balance and compatibility with the environment (Lazić and Popović, 2015). The necessity to complete the natural cycle of matter, in which the end of one cycle ushers in the start of the following, gave rise to the concept of biodegradable polymers made from renewable sources, or biopolymers (Popović et al., 2018).

Biopolymers fall into three broad categories (Fabra et al., 2014; Šuput et al., 2021):

1. Biopolymers extracted from biomass such as agricultural, animal processing, forest or ocean waste, e.g. polysaccharides and proteins of vegetable or animal origin. They are usually classified according to the dominant building material. The main groups of chemical compounds, which serve as sources for biopolymers extracted from biomass, are polysaccharides, proteins and lipids.
2. Polymers artificially synthesized using biological or bio-produced monomer units via classical polymer synthesis routes, for example, polylactic acid or polylactide (PLA), bio-based polyethylene terephthalate (Bio-PET) and biopolyolefins.
3. Polymers produced from wild or genetically modified microorganisms, for example, bacterial cellulose and polyhydroxyalkanoates (PNAs) such as polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB), polyhydroxyvalerate (PHV), and poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV).

Rearranging the polymer chains in the film matrix and lowering the molecular weight are both steps in the preparation of biopolymer films. The polymer chains are first dissolved in a suitable solvent, and as a result, new hydrophilic and hydrogen bonds, as well as ionic or electrostatic attraction, are generated during the evaporation process. Due to the high concentration of reactive side chains in polysaccharide and protein solutions, the networking process is intense, resulting in the development of stiff and brittle films. Plasticizer molecules can be added to biopolymer films to improve their qualities by dispersing throughout the matrix structure of the film and giving the produced film an appearance of flexibility and extensibility (Popović et al., 2018).

Application of biopolymers is wide and includes coatings and films. Coatings application implies forming a biopolymer layer directly on the surface of food product by spraying, dipping or coating, whereas films are self-standing structures which are applied after being formed separately (Šuput et al., 2015).

Biopolymer films and coatings can be used to coat food, separate ingredients, form a barrier against oxygen, flavors, oils and moisture. Biopolymer films and coatings can protect food from light-induced chemical changes, oxidation of nutrients, moisture loss, and surface microbial growth. They can also improve the visual and tactile qualities of product surfaces (Popović et al., 2018). Apart from these important application examples, they can be used as carriers of functional active agents because they have the effect of a matrix for encapsulation that is reflected in the required minimum doses, limited volatility and controlled and gradual release of active components from the food surface (Bonilla et al., 2013).

In this way, their function is reflected in the protection of food products from oxidation and microbiological spoilage, which leads to an improvement in the quality and improvement of the safety of the packaged product. Besides, if edible films and coatings are produced from edible biopolymers and food-grade additives they can be consumed alongside food, providing additional nutrients, possibly enhancing sensory qualities and may include quality-enhancing antimicrobials (Šuput et al., 2015).

Packaging plays a pivotal role in product protection, but its extensive usage raises significant environmental concerns. The utilization of conventional materials like plastics in packaging contributes to pollution and waste accumulation. Consequently, a pressing need exists to transition towards sustainable materials such as biopolymers.

At present, a crucially unexplored domain within this field pertains to the potential of printing on biopolymers, which holds significant importance in enabling the utilization of these materials for packaging products requiring informative labelling. This investigation will shed light on the possibility of printing on biopolymers, chitosan, and gelatin, demonstrating their potential as eco-friendly alternatives for various applications. Successful printing on these biopolymers can unlock numerous opportunities.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Sample

Chitosan and gelatin were selected as the materials for the samples.

Chitosan film: Chitosan film-forming solution was prepared by dissolving chitosan powder in acetic acid (1 % volume concentration) to reach chitosan mass per volume ratio of 10 kg/m³. The solution was left stirring overnight on a magnetic stirrer to dissolve chitosan. Film-forming solution was filtered and poured into Petri dishes (20 g per dish) and dried at room temperature.

Gelatin film: Aqueous gelatin solution 10% (w/w) was prepared and left for 30 minutes at room temperature to undergo gelation, and then dissolved in a water bath at 50°C for about 20 min. Afterwards, 0.1 g glycerol/g gelatin was added and stirred. Film forming solution was poured into Petri dishes (20 g per dish) and dried at room temperature.

2.2 Printing

In order to conduct the experiment, a test chart was designed and depicted in Figure 1. This test chart comprises a QR code, lines, text, and solid fields of primary (CMYK) colours. The lines and text were utilized to visually assess the printability, while the QR code was employed to verify the readability of the encoded data, thereby assessing the print sharpness. Colour patches are only visually analysed.

Figure 1. Test chart used in experiment.

The chosen printing technique in this case was the UVLED printing technology, specifically Apex 1610 machine, was employed.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 illustrates the appearance of the printed samples. The visual evaluation indicates that ink bleeding occurred when printing on gelatin, while notably superior print quality was attained on the chitosan substrate. Both substrates allowed legibility of 4 pt text, while the smallest text (2 pt) was only barely visible. For optimal text printing, a sans-serif font size of 4 pt (using Roboto font) would be recommended as the lower limit.

The lines were precisely and sharply printed, even at a thinness of 0.176 mm, and remained clearly visible on both substrates.

Despite ink bleeding on the gelatin substrate, successful QR code reading was achieved with both substrates. The reading was performed under typical conditions that an average consumer would use, such as daylight illumination and a distance necessary for the camera to achieve optimal focus. The experiment involved two mobile phones, one running the IOS operating system and the other with Android.

Furthermore, it is noteworthy that colour printing is feasible on these substrates as they are transparent and do not interfere with the colour output.

Figure 2. Printed and digitized samples.

4 CONCLUSION

This research will contribute to an improved understanding of the feasibility of printing on biopolymers as a sustainable packaging approach. Discovering solutions for printing on these materials can significantly mitigate the adverse

environmental impacts of packaging while providing essential information to consumers. Advancements in this field can promote sustainable practices in the industry and support the transition towards a more ecologically responsible future. Ultimately, the findings of this research can serve as a foundation for further innovations in packaging and material applications.

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